

Improving Human Resource-Based Energy Security at The Indonesia-Timor Leste Border

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Abstract: PLBN Motaain is one of three cross-border posts built in East Nusa Tenggara Province which are useful not only to maintain the security of Indonesia's borders but also to improve the regional economy. The benefits of the Motaain PLBN include the benefits that trade costs have changed, namely becoming cheaper, the intensity of trade has increased, per capita income, has increased, and economic growth as a result of the development of the Motaain PLBN is very broad both on a micro, mezzo and macro scale. Motaain's PLBN must also be supported by strong and sustainable energy security. The energy security of an area must be supported by the adequate quality of human resources. With the quality of human resources in East Nusa Tenggara which is still low, it is necessary to improve through education reform so that the increase in energy security can be the fastest to encourage the regional economy.

Keywords: energy security, human resources, PLBN, Indonesia, Timor Leste

I. INTRODUCTION

Solving energy problems in an area requires assets called resources. These resources consist of energy resources and human resources. Energy resources are natural resources that can be processed by humans so that they can be used to meet energy needs. In processing energy resources, reliable and competent human resources are needed in the field of energy processing. Quality human resources will accelerate the development of energy resources in an area, which will also directly have an impact on energy security in the region. Thus, the existence of reliable human resources is very necessary because human resources are the main element that determines the success of the implementation of energy security.

Energy security is a condition of ensuring the availability of energy and public access to energy needs that can be obtained at affordable prices and of good or acceptable quality, through a healthy and sustainable energy mix. The concept of energy security adopted by the Indonesian people is 4A1S. 4 A consists of availability, how physical availability; accessibility, how easy it is to get it; affordability, how affordable it is; and acceptability, how is the acceptance of society. 1S is a discussion of energy security through the elements of the energy mix and the sustainability of the existing energy supply-demand system.

Currently, there are still gaps in the condition of energy security between regions in Indonesia, especially in border areas. The gap is in the form of still difficult access and development of the energy sector in border areas. This gap must be addressed immediately, namely by developing an energy strategy to increase energy security in the Border region. Energy access needs to be improved to provide energy for residents in small islands, outer islands, and areas bordering neighboring countries.

Energy security in border areas can be implemented by developing energy resources in the area. This of course must be accompanied by the presence of quality human resources. In this regard, the National Electricity and Energy Management Agency stated the importance of the human resource aspect as implementing and supporting energy infrastructure. This paper discusses the role of human resources at the border between Indonesia and Timor Leste, especially the Motaain State Border Post (PLBN Motaain), in increasing the energy security of the border area.

II. METHOD

This type of research is a literature review, which is a series of studies related to library data collection methods, or research whose research objects are taken from observations of previous research. Data collection is done through various library information (books, encyclopedias, scientific journals, newspapers, magazines, and official documents)

that examines or critically examines the knowledge, ideas, or findings contained in the body of academically oriented.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 PLBN MOTAAIN

Cross-border posts (PLBN) are posts and checkpoints for the entry and exit of people and goods between two countries. Cross-border posts are built in the border area of the country's territory which is located along the Indonesian state border with other countries. In terms of borders with other countries on land. The cross-Border Post is an increase in the function of the Cross-Border Checkpoint, which has and provides services in the fields of immigration, customs, quarantine, security, and management administration. related Cross-border posts are the main system that serves border community activities, especially those of cross-border activities.

The construction of the cross-border post started in 2015. This year the construction of the first seven PLBNs began. Meanwhile, the construction of the second wave began in 2019 with eleven cross-border posts. The construction of cross-border posts is not only aimed at cross-border posts but will also be encouraged to become a new center of economic growth that can improve the welfare of people in border areas. In addition to building departure inspection facilities, checkpoint buildings, utility buildings, confiscated warehouses, and monuments, other supporting facilities were also built, namely border parallel roads, cross-border post access, and housing infrastructure development in border areas.

PLBN Motaain is one of three cross-border posts built in East Nusa Tenggara Province. The Motaain Integrated Cross-Border Post is located in Belu Regency (Indonesia) which is directly adjacent to the Democratic Republic of Timor Leste along 126 KM. Belu Regency has two official gates as gateways on the Indonesia-Timor Leste border, namely Motaain and Turiskain.

The PLBN Motaain building consists of two zones, namely the core zone and the support zone. The core zone is used for the implementation of cross-border services in the form of customs, immigration, quarantine, and security in an integrated manner. In the core zone, there are main buildings, checkpoints, car washes, cargo buildings, weighbridges, cargo scanners, and other buildings as the main inspection facilities for cross-border services. In the support zone, there is a parking lot for officers, and a cross-border monument as well as a market that has been operating for eight months, since it was first opened on September 3, 2019. This market functions to facilitate trade, especially helping Indonesian border communities to sell local commodities that are expected to help boost growth border economy.

Fig 1. Map of the PLBN Motaain area.

One of the impacts of infrastructure development in border areas is that it can support all forms of activities, including cross-border activities and trade. The development of the PLBN Motaain in addition to being able to increase the dignity of the Indonesian nation, is also able to improve the economy, especially the trade sector, not only in the Motaain border area but also has an impact on improving the economy of the community. Belu District. The development of PLBN Motaain has micro, mezzo, and macro impacts on trade activities which include trade costs, tradeintensity, per capita income, and economic growth. As for some of these benefits, namely the cost of trade has

changed, namely becoming cheaper, increasing trade intensity, increasing per capita income, economic growth due to the development of the PLBN Motaain is very broad, both on the micro, mezzo, and macro scales.

3.2 QUALITY OF HUMAN RESOURCES AT PLBN MOTAAIN

Human resources are the key to the growth and development of a country both macro and micro. The existence of quality human resources is the driving force behind the running of a system. About relations between countries, Post Borders is a strategic environment that reflects the conditions and relations between countries. One of the cases that became the focus was the quality of human resources at the Motaain Cross-Border Post (PLBN Motaain).

In optimizing the potential and exploration of the border areas of Indonesia, Timor Leste, Motaain, superior human resources are needed who can read the situation and conditions both in terms of natural resources and human resources between the two countries. As a form of support is the development of a support system for the National Cross-Border Post which includes settlements including 4 strategic sectors, namely drinking water, wastewater, sanitation, and environmental roads. Another thing that is used to support the quality of human resources at cross-border posts is in the development and management of the Mota'ain PLBN Market. If seen from the data, the quality of the Human Resources of the Transboundary Post can be categorized based on the unemployment rate, the percentage of the poor, the human development index, education, and trade.

At the provincial level, the open unemployment rate in East Nusa Tenggara reached 2.8% in February and 4.28% in August with the poor reaching 20.9% in March. In terms of education, it can be broken down into the average length of schooling and the expected length of schooling in each district/city. Especially for Kota Belu, which is the location of the National Border Post, the average length of schooling from 2017 to 2019 has increased by 7.07, 7.08, and 7.11 years, respectively. Meanwhile, the expected length of schooling in Kota Belu also increased from the same range of 12.24, 12.25, and 12.26 years. This is in line with the increase in the human development index of Belu City which increased in 2017-2019 by 61.44, 61.86, and 62.54, respectively. From an economic perspective, it can be seen from the export-import data of the province as follows.

Table 1. Development of Export Import Value of East Nusa Tenggara Province (US\$) in 2020.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mey	June	July	August	Sep	Oct
Impor	7969600	8192779	8067694	3378671	25	855000	125754	143209	642079	2302455
Ekspor	1663744	1467212	1064530	332745	673040	1282576	1554905	1555854	1755228	1586294

Table 1 shows Timor Leste's contribution in terms of trade with Indonesia. Indonesia's exports and imports to Timor Leste in the 2017-2019 range are based on value and volume. Where the volume and value of imports from Timor Leste are 2068125 kg, 2669061 kg, 3444846 kg, and 649782, 1257162, 1401556 USD. Meanwhile, the volume and value of exports to Timor Leste were 93589286 kg, 69136105 kg, 68493402.15 kg, and 22668347, 17800620, 16279934.15 USD.

From the data above, it can be seen that East Nusa Tenggara is still more fortunate than Timor Leste. Where the country is still dependent on oil and gas resources which are shared with Australia as the manager. On a macro basis, Timor Leste's GDP per capita is estimated at US\$2,356 or around Rp. 34.23 million (exchange rate of Rp. 14,532) in December 2020. Still below Indonesia's 2019 per capita income of US\$4,174.9 or around Rp. 60 million. However, Timor Leste's fiscal balance is poor, due to the ever-increasing public spending budget. The Government of Timor Leste has also disbursed 250 million from the Petroleum Fund, 60 percent of which is used for handling Covid-19. In 2019, Timor Leste's oil production reached 38 million barrels of oil equivalent (BOE), which is widely collaborated with Australia. Meanwhile, citing data from the Timor Leste Economic Report released by the World Bank in April 2020, Timor Leste's economy will continue to decline in 2020 due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic and unstable political condition.

3.3 Improving Energy Security At The Ntt-Timor Leste Border (Mota'ain) Human Resources Based

Improving the quality of borders from all sectors is currently the government's concern, not least in the border areas of NTT and Timor Leste, where the PLBN Motaain was built. To support the performance of PLBN and the surrounding community, an optimal supply of energy is needed, both electricity and fuel. As we know the availability sufficient energy in an area will move the economy in that area so that it can affect many aspects, one of which is defense. Therefore, it is necessary to increase energy security (4A+1S) to support efforts to improve the quality of the

border, especially the NTT-Timor Leste border, especially the PLBN Motaain located on Timor Island.

Based on the terminology related to energy security, there are two terms, namely short-term energy security, namely energy security which refers to "supply security" especially during emergencies, such as natural disasters, and long-term energy security, namely energy security related to the supply and utilization of energy security. Energy is compatible with economic development and environmental constraints. Therefore, it is important to carry out energy planning in the future to strengthen energy security which is seen from two aspects, namely macro aspects and micro aspects. The macro aspect consists of 4A+1S (Availability, Acceptability, Accessibility, Affordability, and Sustainability) parameters which are short term, while the micro aspect consists of regulatory, economic, science and technology aspects, socio-political, environmental, security and the most important aspect is human resources. and management (Nurrohim, 2012).

3.3.1 MACRO ASPECTS OF ENERGY SECURITY IN EAST NUSA TENGGARA

A. AVAILABILITY

East Nusa Tenggara has abundant energy resources where one of the border areas between Indonesia and Timor Leste is the Timor Gap which is an area of waters between the islands of Timor, Indonesia, and Australia which is estimated to contain oil reserves of 5 billion barrels and natural gas deposits of around 5 trillion cubic feet. Gas reserves are equivalent to one-third of world gas consumption per year. In addition, East Nusa Tenggara Province also has the potential for renewable energy such as geothermal, water, biomass, solar, and wind power. NTT's geothermal potential is around 1,334.5 MW spread over 24 locations namely Wai Sano Manggarai Barat, UlumbuManggarai Barat, Wai PesiManggarai Barat, Gou - InelikaNgada, MengerudaNgada, MatalokoNgada, Komandaru Ende, Ndetusoko, Sukoria Ende, Jopu Ende, Lesugolo, Oka-Ile Angie Flores Timur, AtadeiLembata, BukapitingAlor, Roma-UjelowungLembata, OyangBarang East Flores, Sirung (Isiabang-Kuriali) Alor, AdumLembata, Alor Timur Alor, MaposManggarai Timur, Rana Manggarai Timur Masak, East Manggarai Kulan Rana, East ManggaraiUlugadung and KupangAmfoang. The hydropower potential is around 68 MW in 3 locations, namely in Wai Ranjang, RiamKiwa, and Watunpangatu.

Biomass potential, East Nusa Tenggara has a source of biomass raw materials in the form of felled Gamal wood, forest residues, bamboo, plant residues, and other biomass including waste/dumping. East Nusa Tenggara has the potential for high availability of solar energy with regular irradiation of more than 50 percent for 8 hours per day and also from the long dry season that lasts 9 months per year. Meanwhile, East Sumba and Ambon are estimated to have wind energy potential of 3 MW and 15 MW. Seeing the enormous potential of energy resources, the government needs to increase the availability of energy in East Nusa Tenggara, especially in border areas, one of which is geothermal. Energy development itself needs supervision so as not to damage the environment and the health of the surrounding community. In addition, the existence of the BBM Terminal in KakulukMesak which is adjacent to the Motaain PLBN also increases the security of fuel supply in the area.

Seeing the huge potential of energy resources, especially renewable energy, the government launched a program to make Sumba Island an Iconic Island. The Sumba Iconic Island Program (SII) is a program initiated to develop Sumba Island as a Renewable Energy Iconic Island to increase energy access through the development and utilization of new and renewable energy to realize energy availability. energy derived from renewable energy gradually by 100%. However, a study on the potential for new and renewable energy on Sumba Island still needs to be carried out to ensure the continuity of the availability of electricity supply in the area.

B. ACCESSIBILITY AND AFFORDABILITY

East Nusa Tenggara's electrification ratio of 85.84% is the smallest compared to other provinces in Indonesia. However, this percentage experienced a significant increase compared to 2018 which was only 61.90%. Currently, in East Nusa Tenggara Province, 63 PLN electric power systems serve loads spread across several islands from the largest to the small islands, including in the area bordering neighboring Timor Leste. On the island of Timor, electricity is supplied by the Timor System (Timor Nusa Tenggara) with a capacity of 70 kW which serves electricity from Kupang to Atambua. The total generating capacity in East Nusa Tenggara reaches 467.77 MW with a capacity of 328.07 MW. Currently, power plants in East Nusa Tenggara are dominated by Diesel Power Plants, especially those using isolated systems, so the cost of producing electricity is still high. In addition to Diesel Power Plants, there are units of Steam

Power Plant (coal), Mini Hydro Power Plant, and Geothermal Power Plant with details of generating capacity in East Nusa Tenggara Province as shown in Figure 2.

In line with the development of renewable energy, electricity needs in East Nusa Tenggara will also be supplied by an electric steam power plant. Meanwhile, to reduce fuel use during peak loads, a Gas Engine Power Plant will be built with natural gas fuel stored in the form of LNG/CNG. The Timor Electric Power System is currently inadequate condition, but at certain times the Timor System is on standby. To anticipate this, it is planned to build a gas engine power plant with a Peaker operating pattern and even a Load Follower using dual fuel (HSD and gas). From the fuel oil sector, to increase people's affordability to the price of fuel oil as of October 2019, 210 locations of one price fuel oil have been built in East Nusa Tenggara Province. With this policy, it is hoped that the people of East Nusa Tenggara, especially the border areas, can encourage the economy of the residents. Although development has been carried out, massive efforts from the government and local governments are still needed to increase energy security in border areas. The electrification ratio which is still below 90% in 2019 shows that the accessibility of the people of East Nusa Tenggara has not been accommodated properly. PLN (State Electricity Company) itself has attempted to increase the electrification ratio in East Nusa Tenggara in 2020 to 100%. However, it seems that there has been no data update regarding the plan.

Fig 2. Indonesia's Electrification Ratio per Province in 2018(a) and 2019(b).

Pembangkit	Sistem Tenaga Listrik	Jumlah Unit	Total Kapasitas (MW)	Daya Mampu Netto (MW)	DMP Tertinggi 1 Tahun Terakhir
PLN					
PLTU	Flores Bagian Barat	1,0	14,0	11,0	11,0
	Sektor NTT	1,0	33,0	14,0	14,0
PLTD	Flores Bagian Barat	17,0	58,3	40,4	40,4
	Flores Bagian Timur	11,0	17,0	10,3	10,3
	Sumba	9,0	11,0	6,1	6,1
	NTT	25,0	35,6	24,4	24,4
PLTMH	Flores Bagian Barat	2,0	0,3	0,3	0,3
	Sumba	4,0	3,0	2,0	0,2
	NTT	1,0	2,0	1,6	1,6
PLTP	NTT	1,0	10,0	8,0	8,0
PLTS	Sumba	1,0	0,2	0,0	0,0
	NTT	8,0	0,9	0,6	0,6
Jumlah PLN		81,0	185,3	118,8	117,0
IPP					
PLTU	Sektor NTT	1,0	30,0	30,0	30,0
PLTMH	Flores Bagian Barat	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,5
PLTS	Sektor NTT	1,0	1,0	0,8	0,8
	Sumba	2,0	1,5	1,0	1,0
Jumlah IPP		5,0	33,0	32,3	32,3
Sewa					
PLTD	Flores Bagian Barat	10,0	26,5	26,5	26,5
	Flores Bagian Timur	8,0	26,5	26,5	26,5
	Sumba	6,0	10,5	10,5	10,5
	NTT	5,0	131,0	71,0	71,0
Jumlah Sewa		29,0	194,5	134,5	134,5

Fig 3. Power Generation Capacity in East Nusa Tenggara 2018 (RUPTL 2019-2028).

Fig 4. Energy Strategic Projects in East Nusa Tenggara.

3.3.2 MICRO ASPECTS OF ENERGY SECURITY

One of the micro aspects of energy security is human resources and management. The role of human resources in the sustainable development of the energy sector to support energy security is very important because humans are machines, especially in developing and implementing energy policies as well as in creating innovation, technology, and expertise. The condition of reliable human resources in the energy sector in Indonesia is generally still lacking. This is one of the causes of the national energy problems that do not go away. The abundant reserves of energy sources cannot be directly enjoyed by the people of Indonesia, but are more regulated by foreign countries. Therefore, to overcome these problems, better management of Human Resources is needed in energy management in the future so that national energy sources are processed more by the nation's children compared to foreign nations as is currently the case. The current mastery of national energy management which is dominated by foreign nations is because Indonesia's human resources to be able to develop the manufacturing industry are still very limited. Both the top level to the

implementer/operator level. In addition, when compared to the level of creativity and work productivity of the Indonesian people with Thailand and Vietnam, Indonesia still needs a lot of improvement in efforts to increase human resources (Nurrohim, 2012).

Therefore, efforts are needed to improve the quality of human resources to support national energy security, especially in border areas. Educational reforms that can improve the ability and expertise of the community, especially in the energy sector, accompanied by continuous skills training are one of the steps that can be used to improve the quality of human resources. With the increasing quality of human resources, especially in the energy sector, in the future, Indonesia will be able to manage its national energy without having to depend on foreign countries. The condition of the border between Indonesia (East Nusa Tenggara) and Timor Leste which is still of low quality and lacks human resources has caused many problems in the economic, socio-cultural, political fields, one of which is the high level of poverty in Indonesia. East Nusa Tenggara. If the energy sector in the border areas is good (energy security is classified as resistant), it will move the regional economy so that it can improve people's welfare which will have a domino effect on the improvement of other fields. Therefore, the role of human resources (residents of East Nusa Tenggara) is very important in increasing energy security in border areas. Community empowerment through education reform and sustainable training is one of the steps that can improve the quality of human resources in the region so that with quality resources it will improve the economy, causing energy needs to continue to increase. This encourages efforts to increase energy production by optimizing the management of available energy resources, especially the use of environmentally friendly renewable energy. With quality human resources, the management of energy reserves can be processed independently and can be prioritized to meet regional needs so that energy security in the regions is classified as resistant which will also have an impact on Indonesia's national security.

IV. CONCLUSION

PLBN is the main system that serves the activities of border communities, especially cross-border activities. In addition to functioning as a state guard post, PLBN also functions as a center for new economic growth to improve the welfare of people in border areas. Energy is one of the important components in national development, including in the Border Area. However, to increase energy security in the PLBN area, it does not only require an adequate supply of energy but also qualified human resources in processing and improving energy security. So that the impact of economic improvement can be felt in a real and sustainable manner. In general, human resources around the Motaain PLBN are still relatively low in terms of the Human Development Index. Therefore, improving the quality of human resources in East Nusa Tenggara is very important. As for the efforts that need to be made in improving the quality of human resources in East Nusa Tenggara, namely through education reform based on increasing the capabilities and expertise of the community, especially in the energy sector through ongoing skills training.

REFERENCES

Journal Papers:

- [1] Lay, B. B. R. J., Wahyono, H., 2018. *Dampak Pengembangan Pos Lintas Batas Negara (PLBN) Motaain pada Kawasan Perbatasan RI-RDTL di Kabupaten Belu Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Timur*. Jurnal Pembangunan Wilayah dan Kota, Vol. 14, No. 1, hal. 29 - 39.
- [2] TM Finambelo, P., Suprojo, A. 2019. *Analisis Pengaruh Pembangunan Pos Lintas Batas Negara terhadap Peningkatan Kesejahteraan Sosial Masyarakat Perbatasan*. Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik, Vol.8, No.2.
- [3] Kennedy, Posma S. J. Dkk. 2019. *Analisa Kondisi Ketahanan Energi di Perbatasan Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Timur dengan Negara Timor Leste*. Jurnal IKRA-ITH Ekonomika Vol 2 No 3, hal 104-110.
- [4] Pusat Penelitian BKD. 2016. *Pengelolaan Energi dan Sumber Daya Alam Nasional*. Jakarta: Balai Pustaka. [5] Angheluta, Sorin P., dkk. 2014. *The Role of Human Resources in Sustainable Development of The Energy Sector*. Ecoforum : Vol. 3, Issue 1(4).
- [6] Nurrohim, Agus. 2012. *Peningkatan Ketahanan Energi Nasional Melalui Penguatan IPTEK dan SDM*. Jakarta: Batan.

Books:

- [7] Dewan Energi Nasional. 2020. *Ketahanan Energi Indonesia Edisi 2020*. Jakarta : Sekretariat Jenderal Dewan Energi Nasional.
- [8] PLN. 2021. *Rencana Usaha Penyediaan Tenaga Listrik PT. PLN Tahun 2021 – 2030*. Jakarta : PT. PLN (Persero).